

Stabilities of Picric Acid Complexes with Substituted Naphthalenes

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Association constants of 1:1 complexes of 1-methyl-, 2-methyl-, 1-methoxy-, 2-methoxy-, 1-chloro-, 1-bromo-, 2-bromo-, and 2-hydroxy-naphthalenes with picric acid in chloroform at 18° and 27° have been determined by the partition method. The association constant values of these complexes, which are a measure of their stability, do not show any systematic dependence on Hammett's value for σ -functions of the substituents. This may be attributed to steric factors. The thermodynamic functions of these molecular complexes do not indicate a strong covalent-bond formation in these complexes.

The study of organic molecular complexes by partition and spectrophotometric methods has received very wide attention¹⁻⁶. According to Ross and Kuntz³, the partition method does not discriminate among various types of interactions and provides very high values of association constants of the molecular complexes. Foster⁵ ascribed this discrepancy to an error in the spectroscopic method used by Ross and Kuntz³. Later Ross *et al.*⁴ pointed out that the spectrophotometric measurements should provide the same value for association constants as that obtained by the partition method. Recently Gardner and Stump⁶ and Foster *et al.*⁷ determined the association constants of some hydrocarbon picrates in chloroform by the partition method with a view to correlating their stabilities with the structural characteristics of the complexes.

Investigations relating to the association constants of 1:1 complexes of mono-substituted naphthalenes with picric acid in chloroform at 18° and 27°, as determined by the partition method, have been described in this communication.

The method adopted in the present investigation is essentially the same as that used by Foster *et al.*⁷ The method is based on the study of the distribution of picric acid between chloroform and water in presence of varying amounts of naphthalene and its derivatives in the chloroform phase.

EXPERIMENTAL

Pure picric acid was recrystallised from ethanol and dried in an oven at 100° for 68 hr. Pure chloroform was washed four to five times with cold distilled water to remove the

1. Moore *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1447.
2. Anderson and Hammie, *ibid.*, 1950, 1089.
3. *J. Amer. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 74.
4. *Ibid.*, 1956, 78, 343.
5. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 5098.
6. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 2759.
7. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 244.

ethanol present. It was then dried over calcium chloride, distilled, and stored in amber-coloured bottles. The hydrocarbons used were either of the extra pure grade or were purified by recrystallisation or distillation and their purities ascertained by checking their melting or boiling points. Methoxynaphthalenes (1- and 2-) were prepared and purified by the standard methods. Sodium thiosulphate, potassium iodide, and iodate used in the estimation of picric acid were of AnalaR quality. The water used as a solvent was prepared by redistilling the distilled water over KOH and KMnO_4 .

Temperature Control.—The distribution studies were carried out at 18° and 27° using a water thermostat providing a temperature control within $\pm 1^\circ$. To maintain the temperature at 18°, the flow of cold water had to be properly adjusted. The temperature remained steady within the prescribed limits for 5-6 hr.

TABLE I
Association constants and thermodynamic functions of picric acid complexes of monosubstituted naphthalenes.

Donor.	K^{18} .	K^{27} .	k .	K_s^{18} .	K_s^{27} .	$-\Delta F^{18}$.	$-\Delta F^{27}$.	$-\Delta H$.	$-\Delta S$.
Naphthalene	2.21	2.00	0.47	2.99 ± 0.02	2.75 ± 0.03	630	602	1608	3.4
1-Methyl—N	2.65	2.24	0.53	3.61 ± 0.06	3.11 ± 0.01	738	673	2859	7.3
2-Methyl—N	3.19	2.73	0.54	4.32 ± 0.02	3.77 ± 0.03	843	787	2615	6.1
1-Methoxy—N	4.59	3.52	0.56	6.31 ± 0.05	4.84 ± 0.02	1060	936	5089	13.9
2-Methoxy—N	2.59	2.31	0.56	3.63 ± 0.04	3.27 ± 0.05	742	703	2005	4.3
1-Chloro—N	1.42	1.22	0.52	2.06 ± 0.02	1.84 ± 0.02	416	362	2169	6.0
1-Bromo—N	1.68	1.33	0.53	2.41 ± 0.03	1.99 ± 0.03	506	408	3671	10.9
2-Bromo—N	1.34	0.91	0.53	2.02 ± 0.03	1.51 ± 0.02	405	245	5685	17.8
2-Hydroxy—N	4.56	2.79	0.45	6.52 ± 0.02	3.81 ± 0.03	1079	754	10300	31.7

N.B. N denotes naphthalene.

DISCUSSION

The values of the apparent stability constants, K , and the association constants, K_s , of molecular complexes of substituted naphthalenes with picric acid at 18° and 27° were calculated from four independent measurements, by following the procedure adopted by Foster *et al.*⁷ The solubility depression constants, k , at 27° were calculated by using the relationship proposed by Anderson and Hammick². Though there is likely to be a slight change in the value of the solubility depression constant with change in temperature, the corresponding change in the association constant is assumed to be very small and well within the limits of the experimental error. The association constant values at 18° and 27° were therefore calculated by using the values of solubility depression constants determined at 27°.

The values of K , k , and K_s in litre mole⁻¹ and thermodynamic functions ΔF , ΔH , and ΔS in cal. mole⁻¹ are recorded in Table I.

The molecular complexes of naphthalene do not exhibit as great and systematic dependence on substituents as the σ -complexes as regards their stabilities. Although the interaction between the components of the molecular complex in a nonpolar or weakly polar solvent, as measured by the partition method, may not be a simple π -complex formation and may include effects such as dipole-dipole, dipole-induced dipole, etc., it may be permissible to interpret the substituent effects in a given series of naphthalene derivatives.

The association constants of the molecular complexes show the following order for substituents in 1-position in naphthalene: methoxyl > methyl > hydrogen > bromide > chloride. For substituents in the 2-position the order is: hydroxy > methyl > methoxyl > hydrogen > bromide.

None of the two types of substituents strictly follows the order of the Hammett σ -functions as has been found by other workers in the case of similar complexes with substituted benzenes. Apart from a reversal of order for the halogen substituents, the order in the first series follows Hammett's order for σ - p -functions. The greater stability of the 1-methoxynaphthalene complex than the 2-methoxy complex indicates that the mesomeric effect (+M) predominates in the 1-position in naphthalene. In the complexes with halogen-substituted naphthalene derivatives, the inductive effect appears to dominate over either the mesomeric or the polarisation effect. The steric effect, which is expected to affect the stability of complexes, is not in evidence in the complexes with halogen derivatives. Stabilities of the complexes show some isolated trends of their dependence on the polarisability of the donor.

Evaluation of the Thermodynamic Functions of the Molecular Complexes

From the data on stability constants of picric acid-hydrocarbon complexes in chloroform at 18° and 27°, enthalpies, free energies of formation, and entropies have been calculated. These are presented in Table I.

ΔH values for the complexes lie between 1.6 and 5.6 kcal. with the exception of 2-hydroxynaphthalene. These values compare well with those reported by Bier⁹ and Briegleb *et al.*¹⁰ for a number of similar complexes. The low enthalpy values rule out a strong covalent-bond formation in these complexes. There is no correlation between the donor structure and the heat of formation of the complex and this is also in agreement with the observation on *sym.*-trinitrobenzene complexes^{9,10}. The high enthalpy value for the 2-naphthol complex indicates a strong intermolecular bond.

The low magnitude of the entropy values is also indicative of a weak intermolecular interaction as the process of removal of solvation sheets, inherent in a strong interaction in solution, would result in a higher magnitude of the entropy values. Relatively high entropy values for some complexes may perhaps be attributed to steric factors.

Magnetic susceptibility data, reported by Khanolkar *et al.*⁹, for a large number of picric acid complexes also suggest a weak intermolecular bonding.

8. *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1958, **27**, 17.

9. *Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1956, **75**, 866.

10. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1932, **B19**, 255.